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FORMING OF THE GAS SPOT MARKET

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ РЫНКА ГАЗОВЫХ СПОТОВ

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Abstract. The geoeconomic processes discussed in article show that the European Union is directing more efforts not to the development of the so-called Turkish hub, but to the diversification of energy supplies and the promotion of gas spot trading, which requires Georgia to take appropriate steps. We believe that the proposals initiated by the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia in November 2022 on the resuscitation of the project for the transportation of liquefied gas tankers from the Black Sea coast of Georgia to the European Union are very timely.

After Russia's annexation of Crimea in 2014, the EU-backed White Stream gas pipeline and the AGRI(LNG) LNG project were suspended. These were the most promising projects for Georgia and Azerbaijan, as both bypassed not only Russia but also Turkey, thus neutralizing their transit hegemony.

Keywords: liquefied natural gas (LNG), gas, Pipelines, Turkey, Russia, Ukraine gas grid.

Аннотация. Рассмотренные в статье геоэкономические процессы показывают, что Евросоюз направляет больше усилий не на развитие так

называемого турецкого хаба, а на диверсификацию поставок энергоносителей и продвижение спотовой торговли газом, что требует от Грузии принятия соответствующих шагов. Мы считаем, что инициированные Министерством экономики и устойчивого развития Грузии в ноябре 2022 года предложения о реанимации проекта транспортировки танкеров со сжиженным газом с черноморского побережья Грузии в Евросоюз весьма своевременны.

После аннексии Крыма Россией в 2014 году были приостановлены поддерживаемые ЕС газопровод «Белый поток» и проект СПГ AGRI (LNG). Это были самые перспективные проекты для Грузии и Азербайджана, поскольку оба обходили не только Россию, но и Турцию, тем самым нейтрализуя их транзитную гегемонию.

Ключевые слова: сжиженный природный газ (СПГ), газ, трубопроводы, Турция, Россия, газовая сеть Украины.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada muhokama qilingan geoiqtisodiy jarayonlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, Yevropa Ittifoqi ko'proq sa'y-harakatlarni turk xabini rivojlantirishga emas, balki energiya ta'minotini diversifikatsiya qilish va gaz spot savdosini rag'batlantirishga yo'naltirmoqda, bu esa Gruziyadan tegishli choralar ko'rishni talab qiladi. O'ylaymizki, Gruziya Iqtisodiyot va barqaror rivojlanish vazirligi tomonidan 2022-yil noyabr oyida Gruziyaning Qora dengiz sohillaridan Yevropa Ittifoqiga suyultirilgan gaz tankerlarini tashish loyihasini qayta tiklash bo'yicha ilgari surilgan takliflar juda dolzarbdir.

2014-yilda Qrim Rossiya tomonidan anneksiya qilinganidan so'ng, Yevropa Ittifoqi tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadigan «Oq oqim» gaz quvuri va AGRI (LNG) LNG loyihasi to'xtatildi. Bu Gruziya va Ozarbayjon uchun eng istiqbolli loyihalar edi, chunki ikkalasi ham nafaqat Rossiyani, balki Turkiyani ham chetlab o'tdi va shu tariqa ularning tranzit gegemonligini zararsizlantirdi.

Kalit so'zlar: suyultirilgan tabiiy gaz (STG), gaz, quvurlar, Turkiya, Rossiya, Ukraina gaz tarmog'i.

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Introduction. Three months before the Russia-Ukraine war, in early December 2021, EU Energy Commissioner Kadri Simonson announced that the EU would create its own gas reserves to protect itself from disruptions to Russian gas supplies (often for political reasons). At the same time, the European Council, at a meeting of energy ministers, decided that the EU would develop a package of regulations for gas and hydrogen markets to replace the previously existing direct, long-term contracts, «tied» to oil prices, Gazprom's monopoly contracts, with more flexible, demand-and-supply-driven spot prices formed by European gas hubs and liquefied gas tankers (LNG). In this way, the EU sought to get rid of the direct, long-term contracts signed with Russia's Gazprom, which have become Moscow's «energy weapon» of the 21st century.

We hypothesize that under war conditions, in 2024-25, the replacement of Europe's monopoly gas supply through Gazprom's pipelines with trading on gas spot markets will continue. This will be a much greater challenge for the sanctioned Russian energy giants than the imposition of an oil price cap (Price Cup) in early 2023. This is likely to soon lead to changes in the energy policy of the Russian Federation, including in the South Caucasus.

Natural gas has historically «recently» become one of the main types of fuel, starting from the 70s of the last century. At the beginning of this century, approximately 88-90% of natural gas was supplied through monopolistic pipelines directly from a specific supplier to a specific consumer, the rest was supplied by tankers in liquid form (LNG). Already in 2021, global LNG imports, according to the report of the International LNG Importers Group (GIIGNL), increased by 4.5% compared to the previous year and amounted to 513.7 billion cubic meters (or 372.3 million tons). The study notes that in 2021, LNG already accounted for about 40% of the global gas market, the rest - again from pipeline gas.

In May 2015, some Northern European consumers gradually switched from direct, long-term contracts with Gazprom to purchasing gas from hubs.

At the same time, the member states' commitment to fill their gas storage facilities by at least 80 percent by November 1, 2022, was overfulfilled. At the end of 2022, relatively warm weather allowed the EU to replenish its reserves.

As a result of the above, according to experts' calculations, EU member states saved \$70 billion. However, they lost almost as much due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war that began in 2022, after prices on the spot market rose to almost \$2,000 per thousand cubic meters. This is about ten times more than the average price of gas on local spot markets at the beginning of 2021. It is also a paradox, but the Russian-Turkish gas pipeline «TurkStream», which was opened on January 8, 2020, protects the countries of the southeastern and central regions of the EU along its route, adjacent to the Black Sea, from price shocks.

By 2025, the energy crisis would be felt most acutely in the Scandinavian countries of the European Union, which had implemented energy reforms faster than their time and largely switched to spot trading; many countries in southern and central Europe, contrary to the requirements of the «Third Energy Package», maintained long-term contracts with Gazprom and found themselves better protected from fluctuations in spot prices at hubs before the war. At the beginning of 2024, the Scandinavian region faced the so-called «energy trilemma» - these are three challenges: secure, affordable and sustainable energy supply. It is clear that, given the unprecedented prices for energy resources and geopolitical risk, supply chains, power grids, raw materials and energy-saving technologies must be ensured in order to meet society's demands in the long term.

The study «The Nordic Energy Trilemma», published by Swedish experts at the end of 2023, examines the factors that led to the most severe energy crisis in northern Europe in recent times. It identifies the risks of the energy transition and assesses measures to mitigate these risks where such measures do not exist. It also proposes actions to address the gaps. These recommendations define national, regional and international actions to increase energy security and emergency preparedness so that Scandinavian societies are prepared for future energy crises. In the study, which discusses the risks, it is noted that «...the decline in Russian energy exports to Europe indicates the vulnerability of over-reliance on energy supplies from one country. Similar situations may arise in the future and have occurred in the past».

In parallel with the monopoly pipeline gas, price fluctuations were also observed in European hubs. For example, during this period, the benchmark European contract, which is the Title Transfer Facility (TTF) futures of the Dutch gas hub, was trading at \$55.81 per megawatt-hour. In August 2022, futures reached a record high of about €343 per megawatt-hour! However, Europe, which was seriously affected by the interruption of gas supplies from Russia due to the conflict, somehow managed to survive the cold season of 2023 without significant supply disruptions. Experts argue that the structural deficit in the European natural gas balance is not yet apparent.

However, European countries have signed several LNG import agreements with the US and the Gulf states. In particular, in November 2023, QatarEnergy signed several agreements to supply Germany with 2 million tons of LNG per year. Also, a giant gas liquefaction plant is planned to be built in the US, which will have a capacity to process almost 2.1 billion cubic feet of natural gas per day and export 15 million tons of LNG per year. The graph shows that not only does reliance on pipeline gas imports drive natural gas price volatility across Europe, but also hub price volatility, which is a result of the absence of a global market price for gas and independent pricing at regional hubs. The graph shows that European natural gas prices increased most during the second half of 2022, especially in August 2022. But the Russian pipeline gas embargo by most EU member states only started in 2023 (?!). Many European countries relied heavily on gas imports from their eastern neighbor until 2023. Dependence on Russian gas was highest in Eastern and Central Europe. As a result, if the average monthly price of natural gas in the United States in October 2023 was At just \$2.99 per million British thermal units (BTU), natural gas prices in Eastern Europe have exceeded the average by about five times US prices.

In general, prices on the European continent are usually higher than in the US, as the latter has been the world's main producer of this hydrocarbon since 2013. Since 2023, many countries have started to look for alternative sources, which has led to a decrease in Russian pipeline gas imports to the EU, which has further increased gas prices there (see Chart 2). The FRED data (Figure 2) shows the IMF's statistics on natural gas prices since 1991, when the data were first collected, for the European

Union (blue) and the United States (red). The chart shows that from that time until 2008, gas prices were almost identical on both sides of the Atlantic. From 2008 until mid-2020, there was a marked and relatively small price difference. After that, there is a significant difference in gas prices between the European Union and the United States. This difference is due to the fact that most natural gas is supplied in its natural, gaseous state through regional pipelines and tankers, and is transported globally, as is the case with oil. So, it is difficult to determine its world price and prices are still formed at regional gas hubs. But the global market is slowly emerging, driven by the growth of liquefied natural gas (LNG) production and spot trading. That's why natural gas prices in the United States have not changed much since Russia's invasion of Ukraine in late February 2022 (Figure 1). In contrast, energy prices in Europe have been steadily rising; by 2024, they are 70% higher than they were in the war.

Fig. 1. IMF's statistics on natural gas prices since 1991 till 2025

The combination of new suppliers of natural gas and relatively reduced demand has changed the situation in Europe and stabilized the price of this commodity. However, all forecasts indicate that demand for natural gas in Europe will increase again in 2024 and the military conflict involving Europe's sanctioned former main supplier, Russia, will continue.

Russian pipeline and reduction in liquefied natural gas (LNG) exports. Despite the insufficient pace of transition of member states to gas spot markets, as required by the «EU Third Energy Package», most experts still believe that the demonopolization of the European gas market - the restriction of long-term contracts

for pipeline gas - is the need of the hour. According to Reuters, already in 2023, Russian pipeline gas exports to Europe decreased by 56%. What will happen if Moscow completely stops supplying gas to Europe? in Ukraine, Russian gas covered 35% to 40% of Europe's gas demand, but the degree of dependence on Gazprom varied from country to country. In particular, countries such as the United Kingdom and Spain received almost no Russian gas, while others such as Germany, Italy and the Netherlands bought significant quantities of this gas. These three countries bought 56.3 billion, 19.7 billion and 11.2 billion cubic meters of Russian gas in 2020, respectively.

It is important to consider not only how large the share of Russian gas in a given market is, but also how accessible alternatives are to them. For example, Germany used to meet almost half of its demand for Russian gas, Bulgaria 100%, and Italy 46%. According to Reuters, in 2023 Russian energy giant Gazprom natural gas supplies to Europe fell by 55.6% to 28.3 billion cubic meters (bcm), the data, based on daily data from European gas transmission group EntsoG and Gazprom on gas transit through Ukraine, showed that average daily Russian gas exports to Europe fell to 77.6 million cubic meters (bcm) in 2023, from 174.8 bcm in 2022. Russia supplied a total of about 63.8 bcm of pipeline gas to Europe via various routes in 2022, according to Gazprom data and Reuters calculations.

Thus, Russian gas exports to Europe, which was its main market, have sharply decreased due to the political consequences of the Ukrainian conflict. A similar situation exists in terms of exports of Russian liquefied natural gas (LNG) to European and Asian markets.

In particular, according to LSEG data, LNG exports from the Russian Federation have decreased not only to European markets, but also to Asia. Russian liquefied natural gas (LNG) exports to Europe fell by 1.9% in 2023 to 15.8 million tonnes, while LNG exports to Asia fell by 11% to 14.9 million tonnes. Europe increased its LNG purchases from other global producers in 2023 after sharply reducing Russian pipeline gas imports in response to the conflict in Ukraine. Overall, Russian LNG exports fell by 6% in 2023 to 31 million tonnes. This was initially due to planned plant repairs over the summer. Then, in December 2023, Russian LNG exports reached a record level of 3.2 million tonnes, of which 1.9 million tonnes were from Yamal LNG. The bulk of the LNG exports were provided by Russia's largest private producer, Novatek. According to preliminary data from LSEG, Novatek shipped 18.7 million tons from the Yamal LNG project via the Arctic and 800,000 tons from the Cryogaz-Vysotsky plant via the Baltic Sea.

The Sakhalin-2 project, operated by Gazprom in Russia's Pacific region, also reduced LNG exports by 10% in 2023 to 10.1 million tons. The medium-tonnage Gazprom LNG Portovaya project, launched in September 2022, exported 1.4 million

tons of LNG in 2023, mainly to Turkey and Greece, and then transshipped three batches to China, one of which via the Arctic (Table 1).

Table 1

From Novatek and Gazprom’s LNG export projects in 2023 and 2022 shipments by region, in million tons

Terminals	2023	2022
Yamal LNG	18.7	20.8
Europe	13.9	15.1
Asia	4.6	5.2
Sakhalin-2 (Asia)	10.1	11.2
Cryogaz-Vysotsky	0.8	0.7
Europe	0.8	0.7
LNG Portovaya	1.4	0.4
Europe	1.1	0.3
Asia	0.2	0.0
All Asia	14.9	16.7
All of Europe	15.8	16.1
Total LNG exports	31.0	33.0

Meanwhile, according to official data for the first ten months of 2023, liquefied gas production in Russia decreased by 4% compared to the same period in 2022 («...LPG production decreased by 4»). The above data allow us to conclude:

- USA sanctions pose a major obstacle to Russia’s plans to increase seaborne exports of liquefied natural gas (LNG) to offset reduced pipeline gas exports to Europe;

- the Russian «strategy» shows that as the world’s fourth-largest LNG producer after the United States, Qatar, and Australia, Russia has the ambition to increase its share of the global market by tripling its output, from about 8% to 20%, or 140 million tons, by 2030-35.

- although Moscow has successfully withstood the export price restriction (Price Cup) for oil and petroleum products since 2022, the impact of the restrictions on LNG will be more severe due to the relatively small number of gas tankers, as well as the availability of technology and finance;

- efforts to redirect Russian gas to China, the world’s second-largest energy consumer after the United States, have been less successful. The ongoing protracted negotiations to double gas sales to China via the new Russian «Power of Siberia 2»

pipeline have not been concluded. It is clear that a new Russian-Chinese gas contract is not yet possible;

- at the same time, according to unverified information in open sources, Arctic LNG 2, controlled by Novatek, Russia's largest LNG producer, is facing delays due to sanctions sensitivity. According to these sources, commercial LNG supplies from this project are expected no earlier than the second half of 2024 or even later. While Novatek stated that it would start resuming production in the first quarter. The annual capacity of this company's Arctic LNG 2 plant (with three terminals) was supposed to be 19.8 million tons of LNG and 1.6 million tons of stable gas condensate;

- this would make Novatek the leader in Russia's energy revenues, after state-owned Gazprom's pipeline gas exports to Europe were halved to just over 100 billion cubic meters in 2023. This would be a very significant change, since hydrocarbon exports provided 57% of Russia's total export revenues and 27% of its gross domestic product in 2023;

- however, the US sanctions, which, according to Russian sources, reflect Washington's desire to become a leader in LNG exports, coincided with Novatek's force majeure. In particular, it was announced that the Russian company could not fulfill its contractual obligations. At the same time, fearing sanctions, Novatek's foreign shareholders suspended their participation in the project. They refused to take responsibility for financing and contracts for the Arctic LNG 2 plant. Arctic LNG 2 is located on the Gydan Peninsula, which juts out into the Kara Sea, in northern Siberia, and without foreign assistance, in such difficult conditions, its operation is unlikely. It is Novatek, which was emerging as an alternative to Gazprom, that owns a 60% stake in the Arctic LNG 2 consortium. Of China's state-owned oil companies, CNOOC Ltd and China National Petroleum Corp (CNPC) each hold 10% stakes, as do France's TotalEnergies, Japan's Mitsui and Co and JOGMEC;

- in addition, Novatek initially announced that 15 Arc7 ice-class LNG tankers, capable of cutting through 2-meter-thick ice, would soon be built at Russia's Zvezda shipyards for Arctic LNG 2. However, French engineering group Gaztransport & Technigaz (GTT) suspended its contract with Russian shipbuilding company Zvezda in January 2024. Another six Arc7-class tankers were to be built by Korean company Hanwha Ocean, formerly Daewoo Shipbuilding & Marine Engineering, but this contract was also canceled. According to Western sources, in such conditions, it will be difficult for Russia to replace GTT in LNG projects.

Who can replace Western companies in the Russian energy sector?

Sanctions could lead to the nationalization of Western energy assets in Russia, or Chinese and Indian investors could enter the Russian market. International oil companies that have operated in Russia for decades have announced that they will either reduce their investments or leave the country after Moscow's invasion of Ukraine. The question is, who will replace them?

Equinor, Eni, BP, ExxonMobil and Shell announced their exit from Russia in the final months of 2023. Others, such as TotalEnergies, OMV and Wintershall, have said they will refrain from further investments in the country.

In response, the Russian government has imposed a temporary ban on all mergers and acquisitions (M&A) deals to prevent foreign high-tech energy companies from leaving the country too quickly. This is done to prevent production disruptions as a result of their departure and to give companies and business owners time to assess the current market situation and weigh up their decisions. If a ban on mergers and acquisitions (M&A) deals is imposed, the departure of foreign companies from Russia may be temporarily halted, but share sales are likely to continue, opening up opportunities for other foreign investors. It is likely that almost all shares owned by foreigners will be sold at a huge discount to their real value. Also, some of the shares may be purchased by the state and thus nationalized.

Experts are discussing which companies will enter the Russian energy sector? First, perhaps, the Chinese energy giants. Just weeks before Moscow's war in Ukraine, Russian President Vladimir Putin was in Beijing for talks with his Chinese counterpart Xi Jinping. Both sides sought to emphasize unity amid escalating tensions with the West. It is likely that now, as Russia faces unprecedented isolation from the international community, its reliance on China as a political and economic ally will only grow. Over the past decade, Russia has been steadily expanding its economic and political ties with China, and energy contracts have played a significant role in this change. More than a decade ago, with the construction of the East Siberia-Pacific Ocean (ESPO) oil pipeline, Russia, which competes with Saudi Arabia for the top spot in China's imports, has become one of the largest suppliers of oil to China. Russian LNG terminals also ship liquefied gas to China, and in late 2019 Gazprom began importing gas to that country via the Power of Siberia pipeline, with an annual design capacity of 55 billion cubic meters. During Putin's visit to Beijing, Gazprom and China's CNPC agreed on a second contract to supply an additional 10 billion cubic meters of gas annually via the Power of Siberia pipeline.

Experts also discuss the potential for expanding the interests of Indian investors. In particular, ONGC Videsh Ltd (OVL) has a stake in the Sakhalin-1 project, from which the American ExxonMobil withdrew. OVL is also Rosneft's investor in the Vankor field, along with Oil India, Indian Oil and Bharat PetroResources. These Indian companies are also interested in the Taas-Yuryakh project, which BP is leaving.

Although the sanctions imposed in 2014 did not stop the expansion of Chinese and Indian investors in Russian energy, many experts believe that this time the circumstances have changed. It will take some time to accurately assess all the risks associated with investing in Russia. But once a clearer picture emerges, there may be a significant activation of Asian business in Russia in the so-called mergers and

acquisitions (M&A) deals, and it is not excluded that Asian players will replace Western companies in major projects. Finally, Russia will likely try to shift European transit routes to Turkey and open a Russian gas hub there.

Restoration of Russian gas supplies to Azerbaijan. Amid the delays in creating a gas hub in Turkey, Russia's Gazprom announced on November 18, 2022, in order to insure itself, that it would supply up to 1 billion cubic meters of natural gas to Azerbaijan from December 2022 to March 2023, under a new contract signed with the Russian monopoly, the state energy company SOCAR.

As is known, Gazprom was the main supplier of gas to Azerbaijan in 2000-2006, but then the country quickly expanded its own gas production at the BP-operated Shah Deniz field, which allowed it to cover not only its own gas needs, but also to export to Georgia and Turkey. With most of its gas already purchased by foreign companies, Azerbaijan returned to receiving gas from Russia in 2017-2018, but stopped purchasing again after the gas from the second stage of Shah Deniz development was sent to Turkey in 2019.

Azerbaijan has long prioritized selling its gas abroad over domestic needs in order to maximize export revenues. The new deal with Gazprom comes as Azerbaijan prepares for a peak in mid-winter 2023. However, the resumption of Russian gas imports now raises additional questions, given that Azerbaijan recently committed to pumping more gas to Europe.

In a statement to the Azerbaijani news agency APA, SOCAR noted that it has a long history of cooperation with Gazprom and that the two companies «...are trying to optimize their infrastructure by organizing the exchange of gas flows».

Azerbaijani gas has been supplied to Europe through the EU's Southern Gas Corridor (SGC) since 2020, with the aim of delivering a contractually agreed 10 billion cubic meters of natural gas per year to European consumers. According to a memorandum of understanding signed between Baku and Brussels in July 2022, the Azerbaijani side pledged to increase exports to 12 billion cubic meters by 2022. Both Brussels and Baku welcomed the new agreement as an expansion of energy relations between the EU and Azerbaijan. The European Commission called the agreement a victory in the EU's efforts to diversify its gas supplies. But it never specified what the additional supply source would be. In fact, Baku was able to supply Europe with not 12, but 18 billion cubic meters of gas! In addition, from the beginning of 2024 Azerbaijan is negotiating with several European countries regarding gas supplies. «The Southern Gas Corridor (SGC) is currently operating at full capacity, and if we want to export additional volumes of gas through it, it must be expanded. Certain funds are needed here, additional pumping stations must be installed. There is a need for our gas», said President I. Aliyev. He noted that Azerbaijani gas is already being supplied to the Bulgarian and Romanian markets. Serbia may join this network in the near future.

Eurasianet reports that, citing a source close to the Shah Deniz consortium (which is responsible for exporting Azerbaijani gas), additional export deals for the sale of gas from the field, above the already agreed 10 billion cubic meters of gas per year, have not been agreed with the operating consortium. In addition, without the addition of Russian gas, Azerbaijan would not have been able to increase gas production from 10 billion cubic meters to 18 billion cubic meters per year for the following objective reasons:

- Azerbaijan's SOCAR develops almost all gas fields - Absheron, Karabakh, Shah Deniz 3, Umid, Babek, etc. together with Western companies. However, in recent years, for environmental reasons, investments in fossil fuel extraction have almost halved in these Western companies operating in Azerbaijan (BP, Total, Equinor, Statoil, etc.) and financing of alternative energy projects has increased;

- also due to environmental considerations, the credit portfolios of the traditional lending banks of the «corridor» - EIB, EBRD, etc. for fossil fuel extraction have been reduced;

- the new gas fields in the Caspian are located in the most difficult geological formations. For example, one of the most promising newly discovered gas fields is located under the bottom of the Azeri-Chiragi-Guneshli oil field, which makes its exploitation almost impossible until the oil is fully extracted. The most difficult geology is found in the second largest gas field in Azerbaijan, Umid, and in the same tectonic block, in Babek, as well as in Zafar and Mashal.

Conclusion. The geoeconomic processes discussed above show that the European Union is directing more efforts not to the development of the so-called Turkish hub, but to the diversification of energy supplies and the promotion of gas spot trading, which requires Georgia to take appropriate steps. We believe that the proposals initiated by the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia in November 2022 on the resuscitation of the project for the transportation of liquefied gas tankers from the Black Sea coast of Georgia to the European Union are very timely.

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